

BILINGUAL TEACHING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND USING THE CASE STUDY METHOD

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Abstract: In this article, methodological recommendations on the use of the case study method for bilingual teaching of English and optional classes are presented based on scientific principles.

Key words: rotate through angle, terminal speed, problem situations (case studies).

The development of such training situations for narrow areas (engineering industry, rocket engines, electrical engineering, etc.) requires high professional knowledge, and it is a challenge for both the teacher and active participants and observers. he says.

New lexical information is successful if it is personally relevant to learners. Therefore, regardless of the form of conducting classes (for example, lectures, practice, laboratory, elective courses, classes with masters), it is not appropriate to present new terms to students in a ready form, because in this case, students are active with terms they don't work. On the other hand, active research in the field of linguistics encourages the reconstruction and deepening of the existing knowledge structure.

In many cases, phrases have signs of a syntactically and semantically integrated unit, one of its components is chosen according to meaning, and the choice of the second depends on the choice of the first and is determined by tradition. For example, the phrase "rotate through angle" corresponds to the phrase "rotate through angle". In the course of practical training, fixed phrases on the subject, found collocations should fill the subject's individual vocabulary.

Among the types of educational activities in optional classes, we include texts and parts of texts, referring and referring to new concepts, denotations, terms, appropriate subject-predicate relations, answers to questions, as well as exercises for finding synonyms. we introduce informative reading. After completing the analysis of new words (language form), it is necessary to return to the content analysis for active use of the new vocabulary, the best tool of which is to solve a set of problematic communicative-cognitive tasks.

In the following examples, the concept of terminal speed is presented in the text as a statement of the task and is actively used in the process of solving it.

Problem 1. A raindrop with radius 1.5 mm falls from a cloud that is at height 1200 m above the ground. The drag coefficient C for the drop is 0.6. Assume that the drop is spherical throughout its fall. The density of water is 1000 kg/m^3 , and the density of air is 1.2 kg/m^3 . (a) What is the **terminal speed** of the drop? (b) What would be the drop's speed just before impact if there were no drag force?

Problem 2. The **terminal speed** of a sky diver is 160 km/h in the spread-eagle position and 310 km/h in the nosedive position. Assuming that the diver's drag coefficient C does not change from one position to the other, find the ratio of the effective cross-sectional area A in the slower position to that in the faster position.

The integrated lessons conducted with students of the graduate course aim to teach a professional foreign language, so language practice takes the leading place, and the content part plays an auxiliary role, creating a basis for language practice.

The implementation of the stated goal of teaching the students of the graduate course allows to attract additional tools for bilingual teaching of the subject and the appropriate methods and methods for optional classes, as well as for the formation of professional vocabulary in two languages. It is not intended to obtain a normative result of learning the content of the material in the form of checking the knowledge available in the special science program. This causes variability of the temporary resources of educational material and types of educational activities.

We believe that problematic situations (case studies) with modeling elements of professional activity have an important potential in achieving the activity of graduate students, including reflection in their minds, working with professional lexical units. Such technology is very suitable for working with future managers, for example, graduate students in the field of "technosphere security".

For example, based on relevant materials posted on the website of the government organization for ensuring labor protection, Health and Safety Executive - the UK national independent watchdog for work-related health, safety and illness.[1] Students of the graduate course are offered sample situations to determine measures to ensure the safety of employees in small enterprises. Preliminary information (setting the scene) for dry cleaners is determined: location of the enterprise, type of building (number of floors of the building, year of construction, location of equipment, availability of stairs), number of employees. Based on the analysis of the company's work, at the first stage, both participants of the discussion of the problem model situation make a

list of risks that employees may face during the hours allocated for independent work. The first assumptions can be as follows.

List of hazards

1. *Use of chlorinated solvents, e.g. perchloroethylene.*
2. *Use of chemicals for spot-cleaning.*
3. *Musculoskeletal injuries.*
4. *Slips and trips.*
5. *Violence and threatening behavior.*
6. *Working at height (eg. changing light bulbs).*
7. *Electrical (eg. faulty building wiring or faulty electrical appliances).*
8. *Pressure vessels.*
9. *Fire (eg. smoking, faulty electrics, arson).*
10. *Asbestos.*

In the audience, each participant presents his list of potential hazards and explains in English how each of the listed types can harm the health of workers. Class work is done in pairs, students make a common list as a result of complementing each other. At the next stage, students will be given written instructions on how to take measures to reduce health risks. The results of the research will be presented in the audience in English.

Summary. The purpose and task of conducting a lesson in the form of a discussion of a problem situation is to enable the participants to learn the definitions of special terms together with semantic relations.

Examples of common terms for basic relationships in science:

Table 1.

Type of hazard	Who might be harmed and how?	What actions are necessary to prevent it?
Working at height (e.g. changing light bulbs)	Staff risk injuries such as bruising or fractures from falls any height.	Strong stepladder in good condition provided and staff are trained to use it safely.
Slips and trips	Staff/customers risk injuries such as fractures/bruises, if they trip over objects or slip on slippages	Staff clean up spillages promptly and, where necessary, use 'wet floor' signs. Stairs well lit and in good condition. Door mats

		put at entrance in wet weather
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New terms and concepts can be formed by adding cause, place, time, shape, structure, physical properties, purpose and other parameters to previously known terms.

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